

Deep Federated Unrolling for Boosting Low-resolution Lidar-based SLAM Solutions

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Abstract—This demo presents a novel Deep Federated Unrolling (FL-DU) super-resolution (SR) approach for enabling low-resolution Lidar-based Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) solutions. The proposed system enhances the accuracy of low-cost Lidar sensors via novel explainable by design neural networks and by enabling collaboration between individual vehicles during learning, thereby minimizing the need for costly high-resolution Lidar sensors, leading to significant cost reductions without affecting the SLAM accuracy. Our demo is available on https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Fp_nBrD6NiY.

Index Terms—SLAM, deep unrolling, federated learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Lidar sensors are a critical component of autonomous vehicles’ perception systems. However, their cost and mechanical complexity can be significant obstacles. For instance, a 64-channel Lidar sensor, while offering high resolution and accuracy, comes with a high cost of 85,000\$. An affordable alternative is the 16-channel Lidar sensor at about 4,000\$, though its lower resolution can affect autonomous driving applications like SLAM. This demo introduces a SR method to leverage low-resolution Lidar data. We employ the deep unrolling (DU) methodology, a technique fusing the benefits of deep learning and optimization-based methods, offering high performance and computational efficiency. The capabilities of the DU method are further extended by incorporating a federated learning strategy, combining the local DU models from different collaborative vehicles towards creating a more robust global DU model to diverse environmental conditions.

II. DEVELOPED LIDAR SR SYSTEM FOR SLAM

Given a high-resolution point cloud derived from a 64-channel lidar sensor and its corresponding range image, $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{64 \times M}$. We create a low-resolution range image, $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{16 \times M}$, via a degradation model $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{S}\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{N}$. Our objective is to estimate \mathbf{X} from \mathbf{Y} employing an optimization problem:

$$\arg \min_{\mathbf{X}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{S}\mathbf{X}\|_F^2 + \mu \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{X}), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{R}(\cdot)$ is a learnable regularizer and \mathbf{S} a downsampling operator. We solve the optimization problem specified in Equation (1) using iterative algorithms to estimate the solution, denoted as $\mathbf{X}^{k+1} = g(\mathbf{X}^k, \mathbf{Y})$. Our approach employs the Deep Unfolding (DU) framework to convert a certain number

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Fig. 1: (a) The DU model, (b) The FL-DU framework, Point clouds derived from (c) Lidar-64 (d) Lidar-16 (e) and the proposed Lidar-DU-64.

TABLE I: Lidar SLAM: Absolute Trajectory Error of the proposed centralized DU and FL-DU methods.

Ouster Dataset	Method	mean	rmse	max
Centralized (a)	Lidar-16	6.84	8.52	25.61
	SR-AE [1]	15.97	18.52	43.04
	Proposed DU	3.86	4.42	15.69
Federated Learning (b)	proposed FL-DU round 6	21.15	22.37	43.70
	proposed FL-DU round 20	7.10	8.30	20.28
	proposed FL-DU round 50	4.39	4.71	9.85
	FL-SRAE [3]	39.2	35.12	71.60

(K) of these iterative steps into layers within a deep learning structure, where each iteration of the iterative solver is considered a unique layer of the proposed model, as shown in Figure 1 (a). The Federated Learning-Deep Unfolding (FL-DU) framework, as seen in Figure 1 (b), describes a scenario where a collection of autonomous agents collaboratively train a global DU model under the coordination of a server.

III. NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

The proposed system is tested based on the real-world Ouster dataset [1], evaluating the performance of the LeGO-LOAM [2], a Lidar SLAM algorithm. The proposed centralized DU and federated learning systems outperform other SOTA methods, as shown in TABLE I.

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